

Ionic liquid and cellulose

TARGET GROUP: This work is suitable for upper secondary school chemistry courses KE1 and KE2 (Chemistry 1 and 2).

DURATION: The duration of the entire module is between 1,5 and 2 hours. The inquiry-based parts last for 1 hour.

MOTIVATION: The work illustrates the significance of chemistry in society, in material industry and in promoting sustainable development.

GOAL: The preliminary task of this work engages into the topic and gives background information on the significance of the work. The inquiry-based part illustrates the connection between chemistry and development of materials and demonstrates a modern innovation. The final task ponders on exploiting the topic in the future, and it's studied how the topic is present in the media.

KEYWORDS: Sustainable development – Materials – Environment – Ionic liquids – Solvents – Cellulose

This work instruction is an entity that consists of preliminary tasks that engage into the activity, the actual inquiry-based work instruction as well as final tasks. The preliminary tasks engage into the topic and give significance for the inquiry-based work. These tasks should be completed for example, as homework, before starting the inquiry-based part of the activity. Before inquiry, it's good to go over the answers to the preliminary tasks together. The inquiry-based part includes background information on the topic, work instructions for preparing an ionic liquid, dissolving and precipitating cellulose as well as questions regarding the work. The final tasks give additional information and a future outlook on the topic.

BACKGROUND

Ionic liquids are organic salts that have a melting point below 100 degrees Celsius. The salts of an ionic liquid consist of an organic cation and an anion.² In this work, the cation of the ionic liquid is DBNH and the anion is propionate. (Picture 1)

Picture 1. DBNH and propionate³

Cellulose is one of the world's most substantial organic compounds. Cellulose is a polymer that has been formed by glucose. Cellulose is relatively strong and only few enzymes are able to decompose cellulose.⁴ The strength of cellulose is caused by hydrogen bonds between molecules and inside molecules.⁵ (Picture 2)

Ionic liquids are one way of dissolving cellulose. A suitable ionic liquid breaks up cellulose's hydrogen bonds between molecules and inside molecules, which causes cellulose to dissolve. Ionic liquids are able to dissolve cellulose in a relatively low temperature. Also, an ionic liquid can be recycled easily.³

Cellulose that has been dissolved in an ionic liquid can be easily precipitated by adding it to some kind of an antisolvent such as water. Water hydrates the ionic liquid and cellulose is precipitated.⁶ The macroscopic morphology of precipitated cellulose depends on how it gets in contact with an antisolvent, in this case with water.⁷

Through this application, it's possible to handle cellulose and modify it into desired shapes. For example, during precipitation, the strength of cellulose can be improved by spinning cellulose. By modifying cellulose, it can be used for many purposes.

In the inquiry-based work, students get to individually prepare an ionic liquid, dissolve cellulose and precipitate cellulose.

Work safety and waste handling

Use safety goggles, a coat and gloves while working!

Gas is formed during the reactions, complete the work in a fume hood. Carry out the weighing on a scale in a fume hood.

DBN and propionic acid are highly corrosive substances, handle them with care.

If solutions get in contact with the skin, immediately rinse the area with plenty of water and soap. If necessary, go to a doctor!

Needles are used in the work, be careful when working with needles.

Needles are collected into a separate waste bin.

Water, containing the ionic solvent, can be poured into the sink with plenty of water.

REAGENTS

- 🔥 1,9 g (grams) 1,5-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]non-5-ene (DBN)
- 🔥 1,1 g Propionic acid
- 🔥 0,1 g cellulose (Avicel or Enocell)

EQUIPMENT

- 🔥 20 ml (milliliters) vial and a cap (Picture 3)
- 🔥 2 ml and 1 ml syringes
- 🔥 0,9 mm (millimeters) and 1,2 mm (1,6 mm) syringe needles
- 🔥 Stand and three clamps
- 🔥 Water bath container
- 🔥 Hotplate and a magnetic stirrer

Picture 3. A vial and a cap

- 🔥 Thermometer
- 🔥 200 ml beaker
- 🔥 Weighing paper or a weighing boat

WORK INSTRUCTIONS

1. In a fume hood, weigh 1,9 g of DNB into the 20 ml vial by using a needle (0,9 mm) and a syringe (2 ml). (Note that it's important to weigh the base first!)
2. Take a new needle (0,9 mm) and a syringe (2 ml) and weigh 1,1 g of propionic acid into the same vial. Note that during this step the mixture warms up.
3. Close the vial's cap immediately after the weighing. Mist forms inside the vial, and it can be dissolved into the solution by twisting and turning the vial.
4. Let the prepared ionic liquid cool down and during this time, weigh 0,1 g of Avicell microcrystalline cellulose on a weighing paper or a weighing boat.
5. Add the weighed cellulose into the ionic liquid in the vial by carefully sprinkling the cellulose.
6. Add a magnetic stirrer inside the vial and close the cap.
7. Prepare the water bath on a hotplate and put the vial into the water bath by using a stand and two clamps, as shown in the picture. (Picture 4) Also, add a thermometer into the water bath.
8. Turn on the magnetic stirrer and heat the water bath to 60 degrees Celsius.
9. Heat the vial in 60 degrees Celsius for 10-15 minutes, during which the cellulose will dissolve in the liquid.
10. Try to dissolve all of the cellulose, also from the sides of the vial.

Picture 4. Heating the vial with two clamps

11. When 10 minutes have passed and all cellulose has dissolved, take the vial out of the water bath and let it cool for a moment.
12. Measure 200 ml of cool water into a beaker.
13. Take some of the prepared solution into a syringe (1 ml) by using a 1,2 mm (or 1,6 mm) needle.
14. Change the needle to a 0,9 mm needle and pipe the solution into the water in small droplets or in a thin stream, and the cellulose dissolves in water. Don't dip the needle into the water.
15. Let cellulose precipitate in water for at least 15 minutes.
16. At the end, you can lift the precipitated cellulose carefully to dry e.g. on a petri dish.

QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE WORK

1. Why do we use a syringe and a needle in the weighing?
2. What is the reaction called that occurs in the third step, where the mixture warms up?
3. How many percent of cellulose does the prepared solution contain?

4. Why shouldn't we dip the needle into the water while piping?

TIPS AND NOTES RELATED TO THE WORK

- It's good to place the scales inside the fume hoods in advance, so that they have enough time to turn on.
- Be careful that the base (DBN) is weighed before adding the acid.
- One should be careful while working, as needles are used in the work.
- The molar ratio of base and propionic acid needs to be 1:1. (DBN 63 % and propionic acid 37 %) There may be slightly more base than acid.
- The amount of cellulose can vary between 3-5%.
- Enocell cellulose can be used instead of Avicel cellulose.

FINAL TASK

Find two pieces of news online that are related to using cellulose as a material. Answer the following questions based on the news that you've found.

1. How does the piece of news discuss about cellulose?
2. Is the news article mainly positive or negative?
3. What kinds of things can be made from cellulose?
4. How do the new uses of cellulose affect the Finnish industry/economy?

This work instruction has been drafted in cooperation with the University of Helsinki's research group for materials chemistry.

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